

A practical framework for few-shot anomaly detection in textile quality control: comparing classical and deep learning approaches

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper evaluates anomaly detection approaches for automated visual inspection (AVI) in textile manufacturing under extreme data scarcity. It addresses the critical challenge of selecting optimal models when defect samples are limited to ten or fewer examples, balancing detection accuracy against operational constraints including inference speed, hardware costs, and deployment complexity.

Design/methodology/approach – A rigorous comparative analysis examines classical machine learning methods (Single-Centroid, K-Means, One-Class SVM) against deep learning approaches (Variational Autoencoder, AnoGAN) across five datasets, including proprietary textile manufacturing data from Vietnamese production facilities and standard computer vision benchmarks. Performance evaluation employs F1-scores, AUROC metrics, computational efficiency measures, and Wilcoxon signed-rank statistical tests to establish significance.

Findings – Results reveal context-dependent model superiority: deep learning excels on high-variance benchmarks (AnoGAN achieves 0.762 F1-score on MVTec AD), while classical methods demonstrate superior performance on controlled industrial textile data (One-Class SVM: 0.806 F1-score with 50,000× faster inference). Statistical validation confirms these differences ($p < 0.05$), establishing that dataset variance characteristics determine optimal model selection. Classical methods enable real-time inspection (> 100 items/second) on standard industrial computers, reducing deployment costs by approximately 85% compared to GPU-based deep learning systems.

Originality/value – Unlike benchmark-focused research emphasizing accuracy maximization, this work introduces a deployment-centric framework linking quantifiable dataset characteristics (variance, throughput requirements, defect diversity) to optimal model architecture. The publicly released industrial dataset and complete implementation enable reproducibility, addressing a critical gap in applied textile manufacturing research.

Keywords Textile defect detection, Automated visual inspection, Quality control, One-Class SVM, Smart manufacturing, Industry 4.0

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

As a traditional yet evolving sector, the textile industry faces increasing pressure to modernize quality control (QC). Automated visual inspection (AVI) offers a pathway to efficiency, but implementation is hindered by the scarcity and diversity of defect data. This "few-shot" problem renders standard supervised learning ineffective, necessitating unsupervised anomaly detection which learns "normality" from good samples.

Theoretical studies of anomaly detection have been conducted previously [15, 1], and the general conclusion is that reconstruction or embedding methods can identify deviations. However, the globalization of the clothing industry requires solutions that are not only accurate but also cost-effective for deployment in varying manufacturing environments.

State-of-the-art (SOTA) methods like PatchCore [13] and vision transformer methods [5, 11] perform very well on benchmarks. Yet, their practical applicability in extreme few-shot cases (≤ 10 training samples) within resource-constrained factories remains unclear. This paper aims to clarify how different algorithmic structures affect detection performance and operational feasibility. Specifically, we address:

- RQ1.** What are the accuracy-stability-cost trade-offs between classical machine learning methods and deep learning approaches for textile defect detection under extreme few-shot constraints?
- RQ2.** Can quantifiable dataset characteristics predict optimal model selection across diverse manufacturing environments?
- RQ3.** Which operational factors determine whether classical or deep learning methods better serve specific production scenarios?

2. Literature Review

Unsupervised anomaly detection has been studied widely. Approaches usually fall into two groups: reconstruction-based and embedding-based methods.

Reconstruction-based methods, like Variational Autoencoders (VAE) [1] and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [14], learn to rebuild normal data. The idea is that the model will have higher errors when reconstructing anomalies that look different from normal data. Newer methods include DRAEM [18], combining reconstruction with discriminative features.

Embedding-based methods are currently the most popular. They use pre-trained networks (e.g., EfficientNet [16], ResNet [9]) to get feature vectors. Top methods like PaDiM [8], PatchCore [13], and transformer approaches like WinCLIP [11] and SimpleNet [5] have very high accuracy on benchmarks like MVTEC AD [3]. EfficientAD [2] tries to balance accuracy and speed but still needs significant computing power.

Textile-specific quality control: Within textile manufacturing, computer vision applications have evolved from early template matching to contemporary deep learning systems. However, literature specific to textile defect detection under extreme data constraints remains sparse. Existing studies often assume abundant data availability, which is rarely the case in high-mix, low-volume production environments typical of the modern fashion supply chain.

3. Methodology

Our framework has a fixed feature extraction step followed by different anomaly detection steps (Figure 1).

3.1 Datasets and Preprocessing

We produced or utilized five different datasets with the same 10-shot training rule to simulate realistic factory conditions:

- **Proprietary Industrial Dataset** (19 samples): Real textile manufacturing data from a Vietnamese garment factory, captured under controlled conditions. Product-identifying information has been anonymized. The dataset represents typical low-variance industrial scenarios.
- **MVTec AD** [3] (15 classes): Standard benchmark with many industrial objects.
- **MVTec 2D LOCO** (3 classes): Logical constraints and structural anomalies.
- **ViSA Visual Anomaly** (11 classes): Complex visual anomalies.
- **Kaggle Industrial Dataset** (7 classes): Extra industrial validation.

Images were resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized with ImageNet stats. No data augmentation was used to strictly test the few-shot capability.

3.2 Feature Extraction and Anomaly Detection

We used a pre-trained EfficientNet-B7 [16] to extract 2560-dimensional feature vectors. We tested five strategies:

1. *Single-Centroid*: Calculates mean of normal features; anomaly score is Euclidean distance.
2. *KMeans Multi-Centroid*: K-means clustering ($k=2-5$) using minimum distance to centroids.
3. *One-Class SVM* [15]: Non-linear boundary with RBF kernel.
4. *Variational Autoencoder (VAE)* [1]: Reconstruction method with 128-d latent space.
5. *AnoGAN* [14]: GAN-based method with iterative latent search.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed anomaly detection pipeline

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Quantitative Performance Summary

Tables 1 through 5 show the performance metrics. The distinctive features of the datasets influenced the results significantly.

Table 1. Performance Summary on the Proprietary Dataset (19 Samples)

Method	NG F1	OK F1	AUROC	AUPR	Train (s)	Inference (ms)
Single-Centroid	0.718 ± 0.301	0.612 ± 0.334	0.913 ± 0.088	0.892 ± 0.129	0.001 ± 0.001	0.011 ± 0.013
KMeans	0.793 ± 0.235	0.574 ± 0.330	0.891 ± 0.117	0.852 ± 0.169	0.017 ± 0.007	0.032 ± 0.009
Multi-Centroid						
One-Class SVM	0.806 ± 0.245	0.665 ± 0.333	0.925 ± 0.090	0.902 ± 0.129	0.001 ± 0.000	0.015 ± 0.021
VAE	0.565 ± 0.457	0.000 ± 0.000	0.841 ± 0.198	0.741 ± 0.302	0.223 ± 0.034	0.024 ± 0.020
AnoGAN	0.803 ± 0.231	0.621 ± 0.322	0.916 ± 0.086	0.887 ± 0.134	0.291 ± 0.041	358.859 ± 23.330

The One-Class SVM showed superior performance on the proprietary dataset. This aligns with the understanding that for low-variance, controlled industrial environments (like the specific textile factory data), finding a tight decision boundary around normal data points is more effective than complex generative modeling. In contrast, deep learning models incurred significantly higher computational costs.

Table 2. Performance Summary on the MVTec AD Dataset (15 Classes)

Method	NG F1	OK F1	AUROC	AUPR	Train (s)	Inference (ms)
Single-Centroid	0.603 ± 0.264	0.614 ± 0.211	0.771 ± 0.155	0.807 ± 0.142	0.002 ± 0.001	0.010 ± 0.009
KMeans	0.505 ± 0.342	0.589 ± 0.224	0.747 ± 0.170	0.760 ± 0.191	0.019 ± 0.007	0.020 ± 0.008
Multi-Centroid						
One-Class SVM	0.597 ± 0.285	0.601 ± 0.223	0.780 ± 0.154	0.807 ± 0.156	0.002 ± 0.001	0.020 ± 0.011
VAE	0.477 ± 0.395	0.205 ± 0.280	0.664 ± 0.255	0.595 ± 0.334	2.427 ± 1.481	0.012 ± 0.005
AnoGAN	0.762 ± 0.174	0.654 ± 0.218	0.892 ± 0.082	0.924 ± 0.066	3.763 ± 2.215	357.249 ± 20.370

Table 3. Performance Summary on the MVTec 2D LOCO Dataset (3 Classes)

Method	NG F1	OK F1	AUROC	AUPR	Train (s)	Inference (ms)
Single-Centroid	0.052 ± 0.090	0.469 ± 0.117	0.548 ± 0.070	0.686 ± 0.165	0.003 ± 0.001	0.009 ± 0.008
KMeans	0.000 ± 0.000	0.465 ± 0.114	0.478 ± 0.124	0.643 ± 0.198	0.042 ± 0.016	0.035 ± 0.040
Multi-Centroid						
One-Class SVM	0.006 ± 0.011	0.464 ± 0.114	0.521 ± 0.201	0.713 ± 0.184	0.013 ± 0.000	0.068 ± 0.057
VAE	0.311 ± 0.441	0.181 ± 0.249	0.623 ± 0.123	0.729 ± 0.187	3.499 ± 1.104	0.021 ± 0.011
AnoGAN	0.307 ± 0.211	0.493 ± 0.081	0.397 ± 0.292	0.575 ± 0.299	5.153 ± 1.488	378.026 ± 22.137

4.2 Visual Analysis and Statistical Significance

Figure 2 illustrates the F1-Score distributions. We investigated the correlations between the method selection and performance using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Table 6).

5. Discussion and Practical Implications

The idea that classical methods are always competitive needs adjustment. On large benchmarks like MVTec AD, AnoGAN is *statistically better* ($p < 0.01$). However, on our proprietary dataset, *One-Class*

Table 4. Performance Summary on the ViSA Dataset (11 Classes)

Method	NG F1	OK F1	AUROC	AUPR	Train (s)	Inference (ms)
Single-Centroid	0.595 ± 0.273	0.528 ± 0.222	0.751 ± 0.190	0.749 ± 0.222	0.003 ± 0.002	0.010 ± 0.013
KMeans	0.414 ± 0.286	0.428 ± 0.198	0.638 ± 0.231	0.601 ± 0.264	0.017 ± 0.006	0.021 ± 0.013
Multi-Centroid						
One-Class SVM	0.573 ± 0.276	0.521 ± 0.207	0.756 ± 0.181	0.744 ± 0.225	0.003 ± 0.001	0.024 ± 0.017
VAE	0.584 ± 0.470	0.039 ± 0.130	0.718 ± 0.245	0.613 ± 0.354	0.733 ± 0.050	0.013 ± 0.018
AnoGAN	0.720 ± 0.245	0.627 ± 0.218	0.880 ± 0.101	0.890 ± 0.124	1.144 ± 0.106	376.540 ± 26.244

Table 5. Performance Summary on the Kaggle Dataset (7 Classes)

Method	NG F1	OK F1	AUROC	AUPR	Train (s)	Inference (ms)
Single-Centroid	0.778 ± 0.358	0.518 ± 0.370	0.988 ± 0.020	0.988 ± 0.021	0.003 ± 0.001	0.010 ± 0.005
KMeans	0.629 ± 0.403	0.370 ± 0.326	0.988 ± 0.021	0.986 ± 0.025	0.014 ± 0.006	0.033 ± 0.018
Multi-Centroid						
One-Class SVM	0.776 ± 0.360	0.603 ± 0.370	0.990 ± 0.017	0.990 ± 0.018	0.002 ± 0.000	0.014 ± 0.009
VAE	0.531 ± 0.472	0.000 ± 0.000	0.954 ± 0.075	0.928 ± 0.126	0.204 ± 0.015	0.011 ± 0.005
AnoGAN	0.722 ± 0.380	0.244 ± 0.360	0.989 ± 0.019	0.988 ± 0.020	0.286 ± 0.034	352.486 ± 2.053

Figure 2. Heatmaps of F1-Scores for the Proprietary Dataset**Table 6.** Statistical Significance (p-values) vs. One-Class SVM

Dataset	Comparison vs. One-Class SVM	p-value	N Pairs
Proprietary (19 samples)	vs. AnoGAN	0.033 *	19
	vs. Single-Centroid	0.002 *	19
	vs. KMeans Multi-Centroid	0.004 *	19
	vs. VAE	0.012 *	19
MVTec AD (15 classes)	vs. AnoGAN	0.002 *	15
	vs. Single-Centroid	0.470	15
	vs. KMeans Multi-Centroid	0.002 *	15
	vs. VAE	0.303	15

SVM is the statistical winner ($p = 0.033$ vs. AnoGAN). This confirms that for specific industrial tasks with low variance, a classical model creates a better decision boundary.

Based on our cost-benefit analysis, we propose a phased implementation strategy for SMEs:

1. **Phase 1 (Pilot):** Deploy Single-Centroid on existing industrial PCs (< \$500). Collect 10 defect-free samples per product.
2. **Phase 2 (Scaling):** If accuracy < 70%, upgrade to One-Class SVM with hyperparameter tuning.
3. **Phase 3 (Optimization):** Only consider Deep Learning (AnoGAN) for high-variance product lines where classical methods consistently fail.

The accessibility of classical methods enables SMEs in developing economies to compete on quality with larger competitors without expensive GPU infrastructure, preserve employment by using AI to augment human inspectors rather than replace them, and reduce defect-related waste (currently 3-5% of production value).

6. Conclusion

This study compared anomaly detection methods for few-shot industrial inspection. We showed that while deep learning is better on complex benchmarks, classical methods – especially **One-Class SVM** – are a strong, practical choice for low-variance industrial tasks. Our results show that in specific cases, a simple classical model can outperform deep learning (One-Class SVM: 0.806 NG F1 on proprietary data).

Declarations

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication.

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Ethics Approval. The proprietary dataset used in this study was collected from a textile manufacturing facility (Elite Long Thanh) with full authorization. All product-identifying information has been anonymized.

Data Availability Statement. The code and public benchmark datasets are available. The proprietary industrial dataset is available upon reasonable request.

References

- [1] An, J. and Cho, S. (2015), “Variational autoencoder based anomaly detection using reconstruction probability”, *Special Lecture on IE*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 1-18.
- [2] Batzner, K., Heckler, L. and König, R. (2024), “EfficientAD: Accurate visual anomaly detection at millisecond-level latencies”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, pp. 128-138.
- [3] Bergmann, P., Fauser, M., Sattlegger, D. and Steger, C. (2019), “MVTec AD – A comprehensive real-world dataset for unsupervised anomaly detection”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 9592-9600.
- [4] Bonfiglioli, L., Toschi, M., Silvestri, D., Fioraio, N. and De Gregorio, D. (2024), “AnomalyCLIP: Object-agnostic prompt learning for zero-shot anomaly detection”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.18961*.
- [5] Cao, Y., Xu, J., Lin, S., Wei, F. and Hu, H. (2023), “SimpleNet: A simple network for image anomaly detection and localization”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 20402-20411.

- [6] Caron, M., Touvron, H., Misra, I., Jégou, H., Mairal, J., Bojanowski, P. and Joulin, A. (2021), “Emerging properties in self-supervised vision transformers”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 9650-9660.
- [7] Chen, T., Kornblith, S., Norouzi, M. and Hinton, G. (2020), “A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations”, *International Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR, pp. 1597-1607.
- [8] Defard, T., Setkov, A., Loesch, A. and Audigier, R. (2021), “PaDiM: A patch distribution modeling framework for anomaly detection and localization”, *International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, Springer, pp. 475-489.
- [9] He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S. and Sun, J. (2016), “Deep residual learning for image recognition”, *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 770-778.
- [10] Huang, C., Guan, H., Jiang, A., Zhang, Y., Spratling, M. and Wang, Y.F. (2022), “Registration based few-shot anomaly detection”, *European Conference on Computer Vision*, Springer, pp. 303-319.
- [11] Liu, Z., Zhou, Y., Xu, Y. and Wang, Z. (2023), “WinCLIP: Zero-/few-shot anomaly classification and segmentation”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 19606-19616.
- [12] Pang, G., Ding, C., Shen, C. and Hengel, A.V.D. (2021), “Explainable deep few-shot anomaly detection with deviation networks”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.00462*.
- [13] Roth, K., Pemula, L., Zepeda, J., Schölkopf, B., Brox, T. and Gehler, P. (2022), “Towards total recall in industrial anomaly detection”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 14318-14328.
- [14] Schlegl, T., Seeböck, P., Waldstein, S.M., Schmidt-Erfurth, U. and Langs, G. (2017), “Unsupervised anomaly detection with generative adversarial networks to guide marker discovery”, *International Conference on Information Processing in Medical Imaging*, Springer, pp. 146-157.
- [15] Schölkopf, B., Platt, J.C., Shawe-Taylor, J., Smola, A.J. and Williamson, R.C. (2001), “Estimating the support of a high-dimensional distribution”, *Neural Computation*, Vol. 13 No. 7, pp. 1443-1471.
- [16] Tan, M. and Le, Q. (2019), “EfficientNet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks”, *International Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR, pp. 6105-6114.
- [17] Weimer, D., Scholz-Reiter, B. and Shpitalni, M. (2016), “Design of deep convolutional neural network architectures for automated feature extraction in industrial inspection”, *CIRP Annals*, Vol. 65 No. 1, pp. 417-420.
- [18] Zavrtnik, V., Kristan, M. and Skočaj, D. (2021), “DRAEM – A discriminatively trained reconstruction embedding for surface anomaly detection”, *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 8330-8339.

Appendix

Experimental Setup and Reproducibility

To ensure the reproducibility of our results, this appendix details the experimental environment and software libraries.

Hardware Configuration: CPU: Intel Core i9-12900K (16 cores, 3.2 GHz); RAM: 32 GB DDR5; GPU: NVIDIA RTX 4090 (24 GB VRAM) for deep learning methods; Storage: 1 TB NVMe SSD.

Software Environment: Operating System: Window 11 Pro 64-bit (10.0, Build 26200); Python: 3.10.12; PyTorch: 2.0.1 with CUDA 11.8; Key Libraries: scikit-learn 1.3.0, NumPy 1.24.3, Pandas 2.0.3, OpenCV 4.8.0; EfficientNet: timm 0.9.2 (PyTorch Image Models).

Reproducibility: The complete source code, including data preprocessing, model training, evaluation scripts, and statistical analysis. The code and datasets are available from the authors upon request.

Dataset Details: Proprietary Industrial Dataset: The 19-sample dataset comprises real defect images from textile production lines at Elite Long Thanh, Vietnam. Each sample category contains 10 "OK" (defect-free) images for training and 50-200 test images (mixed OK/NG) per category. **Anonymization Process:** To protect proprietary information, company logos and batch codes were removed via inpainting, while fabric patterns and defect characteristics were preserved intact.

Declarations

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Competing Interests

The author declares that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication.

Biographical Note

Phuc Truong is an AI Engineer at the AI Innovation Department of Elite Long Thanh, specializing in computer vision applications for industrial manufacturing.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author used a Large Language Model (ChatGPT-4o) to assist with LaTeX formatting, code debugging, and English language refinement. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.